

**BUSINESS
SUSTAINABILITY
— AND —
THE UNITED NATIONS
SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT
GOALS
(UN SDGs)**

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INTRODUCTORY

“Protecting our planet is an imperative for us all, and not least for business. Accounting and finance professionals play a very important role here. They can use their specialist knowledge and expertise to support and advise businesses in developing sustainable solutions.

The pandemic has shown how vital digital transformation is for working in today’s global economy, and in shaping the future of the accounting and finance profession. But how can it play a part in building sustainable solutions and how should the profession respond?

In this report, The Business Standard, with the support of ACCA, has gathered expert opinions from accounting and finance professionals to highlight the actions needed to bring about change, and in particular, to support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.”

EDITOR'S ENOTE

About seven years ago, countries met at a historic UN Summit and set some goals known as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for humanity to survive. It was pledged that countries would marshal their highest resources to achieve these goals to end poverty and inequality and tackle climate change challenges by 2030.

For these goals to be achieved, it is imperative that the private sector business have to work together alongside government efforts.

Private businesses have a big stake here because unless they pay better with fair employment, poverty and inequality cannot be mitigated. Their actions will decide whether we will be able to avert a global climate disaster that is staring down so fiercely at the humanity today. Companies have to be responsible to create a sustainable world.

Their such actions will create new business opportunities as newer technologies will evolve and applied. So the SDG goals now beacon newer horizon of business.

We have to act now because time is running short.

Inam Ahmed

Md Arif Al Islam FCCA

MD & CEO, Summit Communications Ltd
Chairman, Member Advisory Committee (MAC),
ACCA Bangladesh

Prawma Tapashi Khan FCCA

Head of Education and Member Affairs, ACCA Bangladesh

After long 17 years of my professional career in finance, I have taken the path of being an entrepreneur. One of the most valued traits of an entrepreneur is to find opportunities that hide behind the challenges. While initiating my entrepreneurship journey, I Co-founder Summit Communications with partnership of Summit Group. I have been leading this company as CEO and over the period of last decade, we have been able to take Summit Communications Ltd to the height of being the largest fiber optic operator of Bangladesh with 47000 km network. The company has also become the leading Internet Gateway Operator and International Terrestrial cable operator of the country. Most recently, a tower license is also acquired which made the company the only operator providing end to end telecom and ICT infrastructure. All mobile operators, ISPs, cable TV operators and Government offices are dependent on our infrastructure.

The Covid-19 pandemic has taught us some of the very valuable lessons and helped us compose a different approach towards ensuring a sustainable business model. Notable lessons being, having better management over collection through online payment systems and prepayment methods, having better mix of vendors and more efficient processes with vendors in order to have better grip over supply chain, and finally all-encompassing technology adoption all across the company.

Besides, the United Nations has set down targets to tackle inter-connected issues - from environmental to economic and educational - which together posed a critical threat to human survival. The aim is to end poverty, fight inequality and injustice, and tackle climate change by 2030. That's why I believe, we should always look for opportunities to take the lead in transforming the businesses in line with the UN SDGs, causing the lowest level of damage to the environment and creating as many jobs as possible. This pandemic has also taught us many ways of doing work including work from home, which can help to reduce pollution and traffic jam especially in Dhaka, if implemented properly. We have now a powerful opportunity to inspire our community and our stakeholders to act as a force for the public good and drive. We have engaged in different initiatives to support the sustainability agenda which is at the heart of the country's economy.

At the heart of the 2030 agenda are 17 SDGs, designed to be “a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all by 2030”. The SDGs are ambitious objectives and targets that aim to end extreme poverty and hunger, fight inequality and injustice, and tackle climate change by 2030. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) says the 2030 agenda, of which the SDGs are a part, is a plan of action for people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership, which everybody will implement together.

The ACCA believes it is the right thing to do to be more explicit and clearer about how our strategy, purpose and values align with the SDGs. Also, as a leader in the profession, it is right for us to make these commitments in the first year of the UN's call for a decade of action. Through our strategy till 2025, we already actively contribute to several of the UN SDGs, and so making a public commitment and measuring what we do is important.

While sustainability isn't a new concept at ACCA, we believe that now more than ever, it's time for collective action. The Covid-19 pandemic has created unprecedented economic disruption, accelerating global problems such as social and income inequality. And as Mark Carney, former Governor of the Bank of England and COP 26 Finance adviser made it clear that the accountancy profession is essential in the fight against climate change.

As we said in our 2017 report - “The Sustainable Development Goals: Redefining context, risk and opportunity the accountancy profession, today and into the future”, has a key role to play in delivering the 2030 Agenda. To do so, accountants need to be trained and developed appropriately. For that we are also launching a new series of CPD for members, which aims to help our members with the work they do rebuilding from the pandemic.

In Bangladesh, ACCA has been working with Bangladesh Technical Education Board (BTEB), National University to support in upgrading the technical skills and employability/entrepreneurship capabilities of the stakeholders. We are also creating a platform for ‘Women in Finance’ forum to uphold the message on the equity of women and encourage more women to join the profession. We are also aiming to lessen our carbon footprint via expanding remote invigilation and online exams. There are multifaceted benefits in the work we are doing, and we pledge to support the nation to reach the sustainability goals by all means possible.

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Kazi Mahboob Hassan FCCA

Transformation & Strategy Expert

Being a Finance professional, I have been fortunate to play a pivotal role in organizational strategy implementation, in the process what I have observed and strongly believe that, ensuring sustainability is key to future-readiness.

To ensure sustainability, a business' first and foremost focus should be on investing in the right kind of people as they are the one who drives the agendas. For example, a business should streamline the entire finance organisation and create a high-quality data analytics centric, proactive and agile team that supports more on business partnering, proactively highlights gaps and opportunities through various analyses. This shall be followed by investment in innovation in terms of process and products to stay ahead of the competition. For example, investment in ERP system reduces enormous manual works and allow an informed decision.

Also, it is very important to drive organic growth instead of growing through merger or acquisition, as most of the cases involving merger/acquisition has proven to be expensive. Adding new products or new customers and also providing greater customer services may lead to locking the customer base. Finally, taking benefit from the economics of scale purchase and focusing on volume instead of profitability can result in sustainable growth.

During the pandemic, we learned a lot of new techniques which we did not even consider implementing earlier. For example, working remotely. This was achieved through adapting to the demand of the situation such as a high level of IT awareness, mindset to work in global timelines and process innovation.

A fair degree of training on process automation, motivating the workforce to adopt change instead of forcing them can make a difference between success and failure.

In Covid period 250m people lost their jobs which is 4 times higher than Global Financial crisis in 2008. The global GDP fell from 2.6% in 2019 to -3.6% in 2020 eroding values and wealth.

To me, post COVID environment will be driven by high demand and operational readiness of an organization. Whoever invested in process efficiency, product innovation and productivity shall grab market shares from competitions.

Hence in conformity with the UN SDG Goal 8 "Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth", we as a professional Accountants must contribute towards an immediate recovery plan and a sustainable future growth driver.

In terms of business, the word "sustainability" is not that short to explain. However, as a finance professional, I can assure you that the main perspective of sustainability is or should be "inequality". Though finance only relies on numbers, sustainability focuses on building business along with doing good for society as well as humanity. We need to focus on only three major aspects to make a business sustainable. First is transparency, second – understanding the goals the business is driving for, and lastly to have a structured approach with a long term vision.

Then comes the Covid-19 situation which broke everything into pieces including the proven business modules and the hope we had in us. Yet, every problem has several ways of solutions as well. The main things we need to focus on now is maintaining the ways of sourcing raw materials for our businesses, making the process of reaching out to consumers smoother than before and fixing the transaction issues to keep the cash flow for business uninterrupted. It may vary from business to business but the key points will remain the same. Sometimes we will need manpower to solve the problems and sometimes technology. We just have to choose the right thing precisely according to our business goal.

As a part of Grameenphone, I am basically working on connectivity. Still, it is not as small as it sounds. We not only ensure human connectivity, but build connections in between businesses and help young entrepreneurs to grow more. No matter what a fresh graduate chooses as a career – job or business, we will support them to uplift their positions using our connectivity, as communication is the key to success nowadays. Along with their growth by using our help, they are actually helping to erase the financial issues of our country, which is eventually helping Bangladesh to reach for the SDGs as well.

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To ensure sustainability in the business, a very important factor is the product or the service you are providing. The product has to be unique or it has to be something for the mass with assured quality. Simultaneously, it has to be very specific instead of being a workaround. The product should talk about its services itself. After service support can add an additional value to the business in terms of making it more sustainable.

In this pandemic situation, there are a few steps a business should take. Firstly, the organisation should take care of its employees in possible ways. Such as giving job security, financial stability and an eco-friendly working environment to get the best out of them. Right after that, the business should look after the products or services they are providing or dealing with. The service should be fast and digitalised as it should not get stopped due to work from home or any other cause. I believe commitment towards clients is equally important for a sustainable business.

Being finance professionals, we convey the message to the board for helping to achieve the SDGs. So that our board of shareholders can send the message to the government. We are more like the economic or finance officers of the company, who looks after the labour market or the HR sector and mostly to compliance the green reporting. If we can do it properly, it will be linked directly to SDGs. We convey the message to the board only, because the board is connected with so many government agencies such as NBR, labour ministry, environment division etc. If our message is conveyed specifically to the board, they will be able to take necessary steps conveying the message forward to relevant parties, to get the work done finally by any means. Which will eventually lead all of us to achieve the SDGs, the bigger target.

We are in the new normal arena due to the pandemic. Most people are working from home over the last two years. To ensure sustainability in a business I would say the most important things we should have thus the integrity, transparency, relevance and adaptability to customer needs. We need to do more with fewer resources by augmenting digitalisation and analytics. We have to embrace the new technologies and automation. So, if we can ensure these things then sustainability in business will come automatically.

As the covid-19 situation is still on we should take the necessary steps. We should increase people's literacy, start building alternate channels to reach people and that will help us to reduce our costs. At the same time, this will also increase people's flexibility and we have to be assailed for adopting any situation to handle. We also need to train people and increase their literacy.

I always try to update myself with the latest development and technology. Because in my profession every day is a new day. And I have to survive in my profession every day because new things are coming and changing it all dynamically overnight. I have to adapt to these changes. While I do my job I always try to explore things in a new way that will reduce my working hours & save costs. So the philosophy I do have is, "If you win it I win it." So, when I do any investment analysis, I always keep in mind how it benefits a customer. The moment it benefits customers it will give the benefits back organization itself.

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From my point of view, businesses that are purpose-driven in order to solve our problems, become more sustainable.

A sustainable business strategy would involve implementing business models that drive change, influence management and key stakeholders on the competitive advantages of being a purpose-driven firm. The ACCA syllabus helps Professional Accountants learn ways to integrate core values of the firm into work so that they can help transform the business into catalysts for system-level change.

It has already been two years since the Covid-19 pandemic started and businesses are now way more prepared in dealing with crisis situations though we are still not immune to Covid-induced economic slumps. I think at times like this, businesses need to ensure a faster reporting system. If you know what you have, what you will spend and what you will earn — you can then plan ahead using different scenarios.

Businesses have a key role to play in delivering against all 17 SDGs including energy, health, education. The skillsets, organisational roles, expertise and ethical commitment of ACCA professionals place members at the forefront of SDG planning and implementation. The areas accounting professionals can influence range widely, from developing new programmes of activity to evidencing major successes, highlighting risk and proposing alternative courses of action.

Business leaders have to have the mindset to cope with new circumstances. For instance, investors used to come to the AMCs or selling agents of AMCs. We AMCs are used to go to the investors for buying or selling units of mutual funds which are not listed on the stock exchanges. We need to be very aware of our surroundings. Then the proactive mindset understands that You should have the ability to anticipate situations facing you. Businesses have to have a system of continuous development. Also, the businesses should make sure that it maintains an environment in which they can groom themselves continuously.

The business should identify the products, services and processes mostly affected by the Covid-19 situations. Brainstorm alternative products, services and processes and if possible, trial run the alternative products, services or processes and adopt the best possible alternatives. Every business is possible to run even after strictly abiding by the health safety protocol instructed by WHO and local health authorities.

We know how and what the business is earning and spending. We also have to know by the virtue of our profession, how the sustainability of a business may be affected. Therefore, it becomes easier for a finance professional to formulate alternative strategies for a business for its sustainability. The sector I am working in is in dire need of highly skilled finance professionals. To be very honest, the Mutual Fund Industry in Bangladesh cannot even be called an industry yet. Finance professionals can contribute to this nascent sector growing bigger and better.

Dipu Barua ACCA

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Snehasish Manmud & Co.

Muraheb Malik Chowdhury FCA, ACA, FCCA Partner

Masih Muhith Haque & Co. (Chartered Accountants)

In Terms of making a business sustainable, the first thing is to identify the objective of the business. To do so we have to make sure our workforce is mentally happy and they are on the same boat of the business objective. Apart from that, gender equality is a must thing to onboard now. Creating or adding value to the business will also help. The objective could be profit maximization, but along with this how our business contributes to the society is equally important to give light on. Wrapping it up I must say Ethics, Honesty, Integrity are the basics to follow beside all the mentions on the top to make a business sustainable.

Though the Covid situation has been really challenging for all of us, the good news is we are covering it up or coping up with it very nicely and fastly. Virtual works has been encouraged during the whole time, in spite of this being a complete new experience for us. As our country is going towards becoming “Digital Bangladesh”, this was really a needful thing for us to adopt. Slightly shifting the business to online will also lift it up. Because due to covid maximum number of consumers has already moved and others are on their way to move online. But the main challenge in doing business online is the consumers suffer from lack of trust. So if the business can focus on that before conquering online business, there would be almost zero barriers to make and take their business to a different level.

The organisation I am working in, we try to practice and follow open culture. Gender Equality is strictly maintained here. Looking after employees’ mental health to take out the best output is also practiced. These are the basics of how we contribute reasonable impacts in taking our country to achieve the UN SDG.

As a professional accountant, I believe there are few mandatory considerations in order to ensure business sustainability. As like, unless you are in a field of monopoly, the most important consideration is the ability to continuously innovate, grow, introduce positive changes to your product/ service portfolio and keep up to the changing market demand structures. Always have short term and long term plans including financial & contingency plans is necessary. Invest in your employees is a must now. These are the basics to make a business sustainable in my view.

As the COVID-19 pandemic has occurred, there are few things we need to look after. Such as looking to promote cost control measures, particularly in regards to slacks or unnecessary costs etc. Having in your hand contingency plans and multiple financing options for unforeseen crisis scenarios. Above all, ensure health and safety in the workplace and that of your employees. Where possible, provide work-from-home/ flexible work solutions to employees to cope with contingencies.

Professional Accountants have an important role to play in ensuring their part in Bangladesh’s march to growth and ascension towards middle income economy. As in the context of achievement of UN SDG’s, accountants can contribute in binding together with various departments of the entire business. Promoting forward looking plans and ethical practices in business can also help. Need to promote CSR and environmental preservation practices in business, and promote stakeholder awareness of related costs. Promoting healthy work practice and stress management in the work environment, play active roles in preventing burnouts, healthy work-life balance in the industry, gender equality in the workplace and during recruitment, cost control by identifying consumption slacks and recommending related control measures and ensuring continued professional development, learning and knowledge gathering, promote importance of up-to-date education in workplace are the most highlighted tjings now to do.

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According to my view, a business with proper cause and visions to not only survive but to rule the competition and gradually make its own place stronger is called a sustainable business.

There is a very simple yet effective way to do so. That is called “Supporting your Employees”. The pandemic taught us an interesting lesson – working from home can be equally productive. So, supporting employees will encourage them to do whatever is required for the sake of the business from anywhere if needed.

Primarily, taking care of only this issue can lead us towards a sustainable business.

On the other hand, the business should simultaneously focus on online platforms alongside offline for scoping possibilities, as it has become a burning need in this pandemic situation. Businesses should focus to attract their consumers online more often now by creating the sense of the necessity of online facilities among them.

I and my business is serving the UN SDGs by taking care of the health and safety portion of the mass through Eyecare Industry. We provide lenses to those who are visually impaired and even support the poor needy people through Essilor Vision Foundation. Our goal is to serve the 2.5 billion people with eyesight issues aggressively which will eventually serve for attaining the SDGs as well as our country’s growth in the health sector.

A business is not purely an all-to-stick venture. Basically, a business is there to increase the profit and wealth of the shareholders. Sustainability in business is not only increasing the profit of the shareholders, it also means taking account of the life of the people. So when a business is trying to be sustainable, it actually works to protect the business environment and make sure that the lives of the people who are connected to the business thrive. To stay a sustainable business, we need to stay profitable and relevant. Let’s talk about the industrial revolution. Now we are entering the age of the 4th industrial revolution. When we had the 1st industrial revolution the advantage of steam engine industries benefited the world as a whole. We are advancing so fast. The 4th industrial revolution actually includes artificial intelligence, including blockchain, faster computer processing, biotechnology, robotics, internet of things. Bangladesh is to be aware of this revolution. If we cannot adapt before then it is not possible to adapt to the technological revolution. Now the world is connected there through sophisticated technologies. So I think we need to stay with the 4th industrial revolution and changes that are coming with it.

The pandemic situation has stayed for almost 2 years. Now we are understanding that it may not be going away soon. A business that survives in this pandemic scenario basically can do two things. The first thing is to get inside matters related to the business like staff management. If we have to buy equipment like software, we have to make sure that the staff are trained to use them. The way we had interacted with clients basically before the pandemic was mostly face-to-face. We are now connecting digitally to communicate through zoom meetings, e-mail and other means. Another one is externally related to the business. Owners need to look at their business models. They need to look for new ways of getting finances for businesses as well.

I work in the finance industry. The SDGs are to eradicate poverty, hunger or getting sustainable energy, sustainable infrastructure, and saving the environment. All of them are connected with finance and they are related to businesses. The industry looking to the way of investment is in a sustainable business that will have contributed towards achieving the SDGs and they also need to be aware of the government initiatives. I think Bangladesh is doing a good job to that end. So, we need to put more effort into it to reach them quicker.

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In business, sustainability mostly refers to doing activities without impacting the environment, community and society as a whole. In my view, the following points may be considered as the important things to consider.

Sustainability from the perspective of the world needs to be considered by every country while implementing the laws, regulations and policies regarding businesses.

Top management of business entities must have a strong and aligned commitment to sustainability.

Business friendly, transparent laws and regulations and equal application of those to all are very much needed for sustainable growth and operation.

Businesses should not pursue short-term gains at the expense of negative impacts on the environment, community and society, and all businesses should try to implement environmentally friendly processes as soon as possible.

In this global pandemic, citizens of this world have learnt and adopted many things very fast. Some countries were better prepared and some countries had to cope very quickly to survive.

Accepting the fact that uncertainty is inevitable and nothing is certain from now on is essential. This was applicable always, but this global pandemic enhanced the probability of uncertainty significantly.

Businesses need to invest more in human resources to prepare them with the needed competencies and to enhance their passion, dedication, sense of ownership and agility.

Firms need to invest in building infrastructure for existing and future-ready technology. Technological advancement is happening very fast in this global pandemic and businesses need to be ready with the required infrastructure.

I believe, finance and accounting professionals are playing a significant role in the overall economic growth of Bangladesh and are contributing to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the United Nations (UN).

Businesses are playing an important role in eradicating poverty and hunger from society, both of which have become more significant in this pandemic. It will not be possible to touch upon all the UN SDGs in a short time, but it is worth mentioning that to achieve every global goal, finance and accounting professionals are associated with these either directly or indirectly. Further improvement in collaboration and partnerships among relevant stakeholders will be critical in the coming days for the country's faster economic growth.

I think to be sustainable in a business there are four aspects – people, process, technology and innovation. I also think a mixture of these four things are very important for a sustainable business because every organisation needs people to run the business. At the same time, we need innovation and technology to increase the efficiency and productivity of every employee of the organisation. So these four factors together make a business sustainable.

Considering the current Covid-19 situation globally and in Bangladesh, I think constant learning and innovation are the two key factors that need to be adopted by every business to operate at this moment. So innovation is required and at the same time ensuring learning and training for the employees of the organisation is also essential. Good leadership is also needed so that the whole organisation can work towards a common goal and adapt to the changes to do a sustainable business.

In context to the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) I think quality education is one of the key factors in our profession. So being a member of the ACCA and an accountant I think I will always train to be more qualified in the business sector. Especially there is a growing demand in Bangladesh's finance and accounting sector. The innovation infrastructure is of great importance for SDGs. That fulfilment required being a professional, being a businessman, and being an entrepreneur is very important. So we should innovate and diversely fight business and move towards the goals set by the UN. I also think gender equality is important in the workplace which is also a cornerstone of our work ethics.

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Sustainability is a key business driver, not just a “luxury investment”. Having ownership can drive it up. It is the best way to create an immediate impact since when front-line managers have an idea or take initiatives based on their thoughts, they are much more likely to feel ownership and owners do not like to see their ideas get off to a slow start or fail.

Focusing on customer needs is equally important along with a positive continuous problem-solving attitude. Taking customers feedback to improve services and give them a successful experience to build continuous consumption will also help. Lastly, acceptance and adaptation to new ideas at all levels should be there.

The major steps that a business should take are, to explore new areas of opportunities.

The Covid-19 crisis has irreversibly changed organisations’ approaches to risk management and exposed significant shortfalls in prevailing risk-management practices. Simultaneously, the business should adopt the nature of evolving constantly along with making inclusivity the key.

These can eventually help the business to grow more and take it towards sustainability even in this pandemic scenario.

For organisations, the 10 principles of the United Nations Global Compact Accord provide the roadmap for businesses wishing to advance the SDG agenda as they face increasing pressure from activist investors and rating agencies to demonstrate their green credentials and positive impact on society.

There remains a growing necessity for businesses to operate in a much more environmentally friendly manner by leveraging technology and reducing carbon footprints. To do so, there are three fundamental principles –

- 1) waste and pollution should be ‘designed out’ of the business model;
- 2) materials used should be kept in use;
- 3) the natural ecosystem should be regenerated.

Our business is also focusing more on product life extensions by developing products with significant durability. This extends the use of products by customers and thereby slows the rate of extraction of new raw materials to produce repeat products. This solution, along with the three principles, we are thriving to achieve the SDGs and to take our country one step ahead parallelly.

The main objective of any business is to maximize shareholders’ wealth by maintaining a profit. In doing so, a business has to remember its responsibility to wider society and the stakeholders. Resources should be used in such a way that it remains available for future generations besides meeting current demand. Another approach to achieving sustainable development for businesses is to associate with CSR activities. Sustainable development can be achieved by taking care of ESG matters by building an ecosystem. A strong corporate culture has to develop so that it encourages reusing, recycling or reducing where necessary. In my opinion, good governance is primal for achieving the best results in terms of business growth as well as having a commendable economic footprint.

The Covid-19 situation has changed the business landscape unimaginably. To overcome this scenario the first and foremost step to take by a business should be shifting them to online platforms as well. This pandemic taught us to adopt technological advancement and empower self-monitoring processes. It is vital to keep track of ongoing work processes while employees are working from home so that deadlines are manageable and consumers’ objectives are still made.

I, along with my team members, are making a reasonable impact in achieving the UN SDGs. We are operating with fewer people and electronic communications are encouraged. Furthermore, instead of having face to face meetings, we are doing it online which is eventually reducing our carbon footprints. We are implementing some small yet effective ideas which were often overlooked by many of us. Such as using natural lights in workplaces to help our economy passively. We are also focusing on gender equality because it is still a less spoken issue here compared with our neighbouring countries. However, there is still more that we can and should achieve.

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CFO, Top One Ceramic and Industries Limited.

I would like to say something about businesses, profession, accounting and global scenario. The first one being sustainable business. A professional accountant should play a very important role in sustainable business. We know many types of businesses that lack proper planning. We should give entrepreneurs the right guideline for their business. So we, the accountants, should be more vigour and vibrant towards our entrepreneurs to give a proper guideline towards sustainable business how to achieve and survive in this competing industry.

So the next one is covid-19 and the adoptability in the business. After the covid-19 situation, we should be more connected with the new lifestyle and appeal of professional and industrial people. We must have a view how the things are moving towards the near future and coming future.

The last thing I want to talk about is the growth of Bangladesh economy and the Sustainable Development Goals set by the United Nations. We all know that Bangladesh's economy is growing very fast and within a couple of years we will be reaching middle income status. Definitely accountants should play a very strong role moving towards that middle income status of the country as well as the SDGs. Because without the presence of accountants and their pivotal contribution, economy cannot move forward. There should be a strong participation of all the accountants whether they represent ACCA or any other professional bodies.

Sustainability of business does not mean only making a profit and growing the business operation. Rather it is focused on making the world a better place through the contribution of businesses. I think we need to apply a sustainability lens to every aspect of trading.

As finance professionals, we can help financial managements that require proper financial planning of investment, expenditure, fund management and ensuring compliance.

It has been almost two years we are going through the Covid-19 pandemic. In this situation, we need to take care of our main stakeholders- our customers, our suppliers and our employees.

We need to ask for receivables, need to know if they are facing difficulties in paying the bills and accordingly we need to adjust our cash flow forecast. We need to communicate with our supplier. We can rearrange our production if the supply of goods is hampered.

My colleagues told to me that they need to work even more while working from home. So, I think it is time to accept that, working from home does not reduce the productivity of employees. Moreover, it does help to reduce the operating costs of the company.

We finance professionals get the opportunity to contribute to the SDGs from different perspectives. It can be in responsible consumption and production, work and economic environment, industry, innovation and infrastructure or gender equality.

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Moiz Iqbal ACA, FCCA
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KHAN Ayub, Chartered Accountants

To ensure sustainability in business, we will need a proper financial plan first. We have to incorporate something to make it happen. Such as, making new sales strategies, taking over new opportunities, managing cost efficiency etc. The business also needs to be modified to automation for the sake of making it a data-driven enterprise.

In this post-covid situation, the world calls for fresh leadership ideas, innovations, critical and new thinking, becoming more comfortable and how more flexibly we can do our work using new automation technologies in our businesses. To handle the current situation we need to be a bit more tech-savvy along with giving importance to emotional intelligence as well. Our coworkers should get an empathic feeling in their workplaces. We need to take the entire world's environment to a different level, using a very different and innovative leadership by implementing innovations to every tiny service, related to the business.

Startup Bangladesh is the only Venture Capital Company under Bangladesh government. Our goal is to build the entire startup ecosystem rather than only investing in new ones. Every startup of the current time is focusing on achieving SDG 8 – “Economic Growth & Decent Work” – in terms of making their business sustainable. Apart from this, a number of startups are working on different sectors or industries to achieve different SDGs as well. Some are in health sector, some in food, some in logistics, land, mental health, agrotech, e-learning etc. We are promoting and accelerating them to get to their goals and to build a new ecosystem with new aspects by our support.

To me, it is important to assess the sustainability risk within the organisation's business model, strategy, finance, operations and even in communications sometimes to ensure sustainability. We also need to implement sustainability in adaptation plants as well. The accounting system needs to be transparent and the value addition process for stakeholders should be for long terms.

Due to the Covid-19 situation, I think the most necessary steps should be to ensure digitisation to promote remote working conditions, work from home conditions and virtual workstations. To facilitate that, organisations need to invest heavily in technology infrastructure for better virtual collaborations. Digitisation of business processes including automation to reduce face to face meetings and manual work. During the time of any crisis, it is very important for an organisation to ensure effective communication among the stakeholders to maintain their trust, boost employees morale and retain market stability. An organisation then again has to reassess the core opportunities because of that covid situation and plan accordingly.

Being finance professionals, we have a lot to give to the UN SDGs specifically for Bangladesh. SDGs include gender equality, reducing inequalities, zero hunger, no poverty, economic growth and many more aspects. Management Accountants play a vital role in ensuring to promote sustainable business decisions both in public and private sectors for effective sustainable value creations. So, we should apply different tools in governance and analysing data to check that the organisation is aligned with their specific development goal as business and society are two simultaneous parallel bodies. If one of them is not sustainable, the other will be at risk. Hence, the organisation needs to do good to the business and to the society and environment as well.

Tahid Ahmed Chowdhury FCCA (UK)
Managing Director & CEO
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Mohammed Sumon FCCA, CPA
Head of Finance
Lakdhanavi Limited

Financial markets are the primary directors of economic activity in a capitalist global society. However, they also have an important societal role in encouraging investments that are beneficial to natural and human ecosystems. A complete finance professional must understand sustainability factors and should continuously review a few things to ensure sustainable business. Which includes reviewing current and future capital, understanding human resource needs determining how to address that with anticipated growth, analysing and working to balance profitability, ensuring research and development and improving reporting as well as planning capabilities, evaluating and understanding the customers and key prospects.

First of all, we need to learn how to survive the business in the current pandemic situation. The Covid-19 is massively changing the business dynamics. It has given us the opportunities to learn how to work from home. We should be more habituated work from home to ensure better work-life balance, reduced overhead expenses alongside travelling costs and time. We have seen around the world that lots of organisations equipped themselves to work from home permanently that reduced the fixed costs and increased their growth and profitability substantially.

Basically, I am an investment banker. ACCA degree has given me the opportunity to become competitive and understand the insight of all sectors of the finance profession. I am mainly advising my clients about financial and Management restructuring hence bringing the company again on profitability and growth. Also, I give advisory services to various companies for listing to stock exchanges in Bangladesh that ensure their financial needs and growth. Listing into the stock exchanges ensures the companies' corporate governance and following the rules and regulations better.

As a finance professional, I think that companies need to achieve short-term results and long-term growth by focusing on their core business and diversification to ensure sustainability.

Companies also require operating their business differently in the world nowadays. They need a business model considering the broader picture such as customer needs, employee needs, environmental and all other stakeholders needs. A company should not only think about the financial return only, but also it must think about sustainability to operate in future.

For dealing with the global Covid-19 pandemic, this world needs to adopt new mindsets and reform the new corporate strategy. One of the corporate strategies is the application of new technologies in all business functions that will enhance the speed of the work, reduce cost, and manage a better supply chain. Companies also should adopt remote work to prevent the spread of viruses. Remote working will save commute time and it provides more flexibility.

At the beginning of lockdown in March 2020 and shutdown of the business operation, power demand in Bangladesh reduced. We have delivered the power during the lockdown since it is the energy sector and I have not seen any negative impact on that.

In terms of the SDG achievement progress, Bangladesh gained the highest GDP growth in the last 10 years, maintained strong macroeconomic stability and reduced the poverty by increasing per capita income. Bangladesh has given responsibilities to 17 ministries to achieve 17 goals. Bangladesh is a pioneer among the major countries of the subcontinent for localising the SDGs. The way Bangladesh and its economy is progressing, it expects to be an upper-middle-income country in 2031 and a developed country in 2041.

As finance professionals, we must enhance the accountability and responsibility of business transitions, introduce proper training, reduce waste and corruption and create a learning organisation for businesses to be more sustainable.

Munazzeel Riasat ACCA

Chief Executive Officer (CEO),
IBC Power Limited

Shadab Sakib Mostafa ACCA

Head of rPET Business Unit
Bangladesh Petrochemical Company Limited (BPCL)

The ongoing pandemic has been a timely indication for businesses that disruptions to the established order of “business as usual” are not only probable, they are inevitable and in order to ensure long term sustainability, businesses need to be fleet footed in their management approach to mitigate risks and grab opportunities as they arise.

The effects of the pandemic on the global economy like growing inflation driven by backlogs within the supply chain and energy shortages can be reasonably extrapolated to correlate in varying degrees with future market disruptions that will arise due to the effects of climate change. It therefore stands to reason that the lessons learned from the pandemic can guide us in our risk mitigation measures in the future.

Businesses are vulnerable to the physical and transitory risks that climate change will bring in the coming decades and need to account for them to ensure their future viability. The UN’s 17 SDGs provide a framework for companies to navigate this future landscape by highlighting key areas where organizations can make positive contributions to ensure the future sustainability of the ecosystems they operate in and in doing so, ensuring their own sustainability.

For organizations operating in Bangladesh, orienting organizational goals to related SDGs and aligning financial reporting with guidance from official sector bodies are like the FSB and the IFRs foundation will ensure their alignment with globally adopted legislative measures to combat climate change and allow greater access to world markets and opportunities for trade as a result.

IBC Power limited through its dredging and river training initiatives is assisting the GoB in its climate risk mitigation efforts and consequently, also positively impacting SGDs like poverty reduction, infrastructure building, climate action, among others. Through its operations, by building readiness to comply with future regulations and lowering its overall carbon footprint, IBC power limited is working to ensure a sustainable future for itself, its many stakeholders and its ecosystem.

Being a professional Chartered Accountant, I believe it is an ethical duty to comply with reports on advancing and aligning disclosure of environmental and social information in mainstream reports as per Climate Disclosure Standards Board (CDSB) guideline.

I am fortunate to work for Bangladesh Petrochemical Company Limited (BPCL). Our company has a firm environmental commitment, where we are working to diminish greenhouse emissions and create worth out of waste by recycling 15,000 tons of used Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) bottles, thereby preventing them from becoming 93,000 m3 landfill, which will eventually escape into the river. We are also contributing to minimizing the demand and usage for virgin PET resin required to produce plastic water, juice, carbonated beverage drinks, oil bottle, and different types of jars and one-time products for the packaging industry, which indeed is helping to decrease 13,500 kg of CO2 gas emissions per annum. Therefore, it is assisting towards obtaining the UN SDG Goals in Bangladesh by reducing adverse environmental impact and combating climate change.

Our company is helping in poverty alleviation too, by creating job opportunities to waste pickers from more than 300 urban slum dwellers, thus changing the perception of how the public distinguishes this group of workers, and above all, changing the way they used to perceive themselves. Therefore, waste collectors are able to be the proponent for their fair wages and improve the living standard for themselves and their family members. Furthermore, our supply chain has created a multiplier effect by providing income to approximately 50,000 people from recycling and manufacturing PET bottles.

We can now proudly say that we have become the import substitute of the PET industry of Bangladesh. Previously, our country was entirely dependent on imported PET resins until we provided bottle makers with the option to source PET resins locally. Thus, it is helping the country save foreign currency outflow.

As a pioneer of recycling PET bottles, we have noticed recycling PET resin has been receiving a massive global demand lately. Because it is eco-friendly and the target markets are highly environmentally concerned, it will help to preserve our earth’s ecosystem. I hope this inspires other industry leaders and change-makers to see the merits of recycling. If done right, I am confident we can achieve the Sustainable Development Goals in Bangladesh much sooner than anticipated.

Md. Sarfaraz Ninad ACCA

Audit Specialist
S.F. Ahmed & Co.

Md. Sohel Rana ACCA, CFC

CFO
Hosaf Group of Industries

Sustainable business model is a vital part for the organization as well as for the communities. A business must be aware of their production and consumption to align with UN sustainable business goals. To maintain responsible production and consumption they need to consider supply chain supports environments goals. Personal connections of business owners to take care of the planet, being accountable, having the courage to improve constantly, embracing competitors as collaborators, setting a long-term holistic vision etc can be considered as crucial things to ensure sustainability. Also the organizations should look at their good corporate citizens by regularly assessing their nearest communities and their impact to them. Moreover, it is also important to contribute to health, better education, clean water and a sustainable environment as well.

In Covid-19 pandemic, some companies were able to gain advantages and some had to close their business. Reassess Growth Opportunities, take multiple perspectives, on-line platform can be considered, expand business from niche market, reallocate Capital these are the primary things an organization can take to overcome the current situation.

As an auditor, I think we can play a vital role for sustainable development. Such as, providing integrated reporting framework and independent assurance, improving company's business processes and identifying ways to reward sustainable policies etc. One great success will bring confidence to achieve the SDG. Bangladesh is meeting the set target in reducing population below the national poverty line (currently 22.4%) three years ahead of time. In addition, the country was also able to reach the target in reducing infant mortality. Our Prime Minister has expressed her deep commitment to achieving these before the year 2030. Eventually, I hope that if we all can set our goals alligned with the UN SDG, then we can achieve it by 2030.

For a business organization, sustainability comes from its smooth operation, growth of its revenue and profitability with good governance practices. To secure the real sustainable development of business, we must make sure that the employer has picked the right person for the key business tasks. In my view, business houses should emphasize to recruit professional competent candidates for monitoring and development of its different core functions to secure maximum profitability with good governance which will eventually help them to make the business suitability in the long run.

This is probably the most important question in the 21st century related to business and industry as we are passing a very hard time. The Impact of COVID-19 has forced the management and entrepreneurs to change their directives to run business organizations for survival. Considering the global pandemic situation, business organizations should prioritize the human forces health and safety issues first. Concentrating on existing key business strengths to maximize the synergy benefits over the markets will also help. It is really noteworthy that this is high time to build up a contingency plan with available resources, financial management system, information technology and logistics support to ensure uninterrupted business operation in future.

Chartered accountants are playing a very crucial role for sustainable development of our business sector and overall community through their competent professional services. Nowadays, business houses are no more interested in traditional accountants. Instead they are seeking a professional accountant/finance specialist who can contribute a lot to their business development through their creativity and helps them to evolve a disciplined financial management system within the entity. This will definitely help us to achieve UN SDGs and overall economic growth of Bangladesh through innovation in the financial management system, establishing decent work environment, resilient infrastructure development and reduced inequalities over the society.

N. Newaz Karim ACCA
Director, Edbase Professionals

Mohammad Tanvir Hossain ACCA
CFO
Somatec Pharmaceuticals Ltd

Sustainable business is a concept that is growing day by day. In the past, businesses have suffered due to having thought of only short-term goals and objectives as they always tended to investigate the immediate benefit compromising the later effects it could bring. Traditionally the finance function within an organization is only responsible for contributing to financial decisions. However, making ethical decisions, understanding the social aspects, and having the knowledge of the legal framework are equally important to keep the business going in the long term thus making it more sustainable.

Covid-19 has been a reality check for many organizations. The concept of a flexible working environment has been greatly neglected despite there being industries where professionals have been seen to become successful with the complete flexibility of working from their homes. There are such things we should start practicing in this situation Firstly, Work from home needs to be encouraged, hiring people from different areas can versatile the business, organizations could hold online meetings whenever and wherever an idea has to be shared, organizations need to move into cloud-based software for accounting and business management. An organization should always be prepared to accept the changes in the working environment. All of this is important to sustain in this pandemic.

As a part of the education industry, our main objective throughout these circumstances has been to focus on sustainability. As part of that plan, we converted our classrooms into hybrid platforms and scheduled our staff to work from home during severe lockdowns. Furthermore, our business motto has always been to promote gender equality by employing a similar number of men & women promoting the UN SDG goals number 5. But only a specific contribution won't work. We all should come from all sectors with what we have to contribute in achieving the UN SDG.

Sustainability is a blend of lots of components and it is a comprehensive matter to adopt and fuel such initiative by any business. Focusing on a specific matter, can't make it happen. We need to give light on more than one aspect. In my view, the following would be the key areas that affect sustainability. Such as, Setting the tone at the Top, Hiring the right resources, Succession Planning, Process Improvement, Supply Chain Management, Business Performance Reviews etc. These should be the primary points to check to make a business sustainable.

For business continuation in this covid-19 scenario, the following should be of utmost priority. Such as, Starting Safeguard for Human Resources. "Safety first" should be the key for any business as loss of such resources are irreparable. Revisiting and Reshaping Business Plans by monitoring costs, considering value for money, alternative finance and sales options etc. Business Process Automation and Embracing new tech is similarly important. Simply a business can turn its speed back now, just by taking care of these small but effective issues.

This pharma industry was highly regulated and trailed back to emergence in the 1950s. This industry has huge potential and right now the market makes a statement of 3 bln USD with 2% contribution to our GDP. My professional attire helping me to get commercial acumen and supporting me to drive business in the following areas:

1. Looking for alternative markets to create separate revenue channels
2. Going paperless to reduce wastage of papers
3. Implementing ERP Systems for effective utilization of resources
4. Balancing the parity in pay out to improve living standard
5. Fiscal compliances leading towards healthy pay out to the national exchequer.

Labio Bala FCCA
National Project Support Officer (Finance)
United Nations Office for Project Services (UNOPS)

Tapan Kumar Banik ACCA
First Assistant Vice President
Prime Bank Ltd

To ensure sustainability in a business, the most important things we need to take into account are Management for quality and excellence, Grow skills and Leadership capabilities, Passion to achieve the goal and for customer satisfaction, Friendly and supportive work culture and environment, Embed Digitalization and Diversification, Mobilize resources and steward them faithfully etc.

We need to bear in mind that whatever we do, we need to do from our heart. Our job can not give us value but we can add value to our job. Do not be defeated by evil, but overcome evil with good. If we sincerely take all these aspects into account, we will surely be able to ensure sustainability in business and it will help people live better lives through innovative and practical solutions in sustainable ways.

The COVID-19 pandemic is having widespread effects on businesses across the country. Despite all these challenges and obstacles, I strongly believe that where there's a will, there's a way. It reminds me, "Good thoughts and actions can never produce bad results, bad thoughts and actions can never produce good results." (Thinking for a Change by John Maxwell).

Considering the above context, according to my view, a business should adapt some strategy such as Start with health and Security, Engage with online sustainability resources, Monitor business continuity Plan and risk management, Prepare a communication Plan, Prioritize customer needs and satisfactions, Maintain trust and brand consistency, Evaluate capacity and resources and 'Green' e-commerce experience because consumers are shopping online etc.

Currently I am working with the UNOPS Bangladesh which helps people live better lives. Our strategy is very much aligned with the 8th Five Year Plan of Bangladesh. In terms of SDGs, my professional expertise as part of the Team impacts to the following SDGs like SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being, SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation, SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy, SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities and SDG 13: Climate Action etc.

Sustainability means "Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" Three bottom line of sustainability is 3P. Profit, People, Planet. Paradigm now shifted from Profit to people and planet. A complete Finance Professional actually a strategic business Leader who not only deals with numbers but also focus the driven forces behind the numbers. A finance professional should take any business decision in a holistic manner considering risk and return in every aspect, maintaining all stakeholder expectations in the long run. As a finance professional, I think the most important matter to ensure sustainability in a business is the adoptability where innovation comes through utilizing the technology; meeting customer expectation as well as improving operational efficiency. From all of the above, Corporate Governance is the precondition for a business to be sustainable.

The profound impact of Covid-19 teaches business community a lot. We are moving towards digitization, shifting the whole business model techno-driven where efficiency comes through automation and innovation, reducing huge operating cost by maintaining work from home as well as "Training and Meeting" cost of employee in a minimal. A business must have Business Continuity plan (BCP) to meet the Challenges of unprecedented event in more dynamic business world.

There are broad 17 goals set up in SDG; on the principal idea "leaving no one behind" By channeling fund from the saver to the entrepreneur, Bank can contribute a pivotal role in implementing 17 SDG plan either directly or indirectly. As for example; Govt full stimulus package has been disbursed through banking channel which helps the economy to be full vibrant during pandemic period of covid-19. Besides this, Banks promote Green and sustainable projects like effluent Treatment plant, Green building and environment friendly Brick Production, LED Bulb assembly and recycling Plant. Banks are now moving to a paperless operations environment by introducing internet banking and also continued the efforts in helping customers reduce their environmental footprint by offering them paperless services through digital channels among various platforms.

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